

Method Development And Validation of Osimertinib for the Estimation of API and Pharmaceutical Formulation by RP- HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A simple, accurate, precise, and reproducible reverse phase high-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the quantitative estimation of Osimertinib in active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a C18 column using a suitable mobile phase consisting of an optimized ratio of organic solvent and buffer, delivered at a constant flow rate. Detection was carried out using a UV detector at an appropriate wavelength. The developed method was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines with respect to parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), robustness, and system suitability. The method showed good linearity over the selected concentration range with acceptable accuracy and precision. The proposed RP-HPLC method is suitable for routine quality control analysis of Osimertinib in bulk drug and pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords: Osimertinib, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Method Validation, Pharmaceutical Dosage Form, ICH Guidelines, Quantitative Analysis

INTRODUCTION

High-performance liquid chromatography:

High-performance liquid chromatography or commonly known as HPLC, is an analytical technique used to separate, identify or quantify each component in a mixture. The mixture is separated using the basic principle of column chromatography and then identified and quantified by spectroscopy. In the 1960s, the column chromatography LC with its low-pressure suitable glass columns was further developed to the HPLC with its high-pressure adapted metal columns. HPLC is thus basically a highly improved form of column liquid chromatography. Instead of a solvent being allowed to drip through a column under gravity, it is forced through under high pressures of upto 400 atmospheres. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), formerly referred to as high- pressure liquid chromatography, is a technique in analytical chemistry used to separate, identify, and quantify each component in a mixture. It relies on

pumps to pass a pressurized liquid solvent containing the sample mixture through a column filled with a solid adsorbent material. Each component in the sample interacts slightly differently with the adsorbent material, causing different flow rates for the different components and leading to the separation of the components as they flow out of the column. HPLC has been used for manufacturing (e.g. during the production process of pharmaceutical and biological products), legal (e.g., detecting performance enhancement drugs in urine), research(e.g., separating the components of a complex biological sample, or of similar synthetic chemicals from each other), and medical (e.g., detecting vitamin D levels in blood serum) purposes.

The principle of separation in normal phase mode and reverse phase mode is adsorption. When a mixture of components are introduced into a HPLC column, they travel according to their relative affinities towards the stationary phase. The component which has more

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affinity towards the adsorbent, travels slower. The component which has less affinity towards the stationary phase travels faster. Since no 2 components have the same affinity towards the stationary phase, the components are separated.

Principle of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

The purification takes place in a separation column between a stationary and a mobile phase. The stationary phase is a granular material with very small porous particles in a separation column. The mobile phase, on the other hand, is a solvent or solvent mixture which is forced at high pressure through the separation column. Via a valve with a connected sample loop, i.e. a small tube or a capillary made of stainless steel, the sample is injected into the mobile phase flow from the pump to the separation column using a syringe. Subsequently, the individual components of the sample migrate through the column at different rates because they are retained to a varying degree by interactions with the stationary phase. After leaving the column, the individual substances are detected by a suitable detector and passed on as a signal to the HPLC software on the computer. At the end of this operation/run, a chromatogram in the HPLC software on the computer is obtained. The chromatogram allows the identification and quantification of the different substances.

TYPES OF HPLC TECHNIQUES:

- A. Based on modes of chromatography
 1. Normal phase mode
 2. Reverse phase mode
- B. Based on principle of separation
 1. Adsorption chromatography
 2. Ion exchange chromatography
 3. Ion pair chromatography
 4. Size exclusion (or) Gel permeation chromatography

5. Affinity chromatography
 6. Chiral phase chromatography
- C. Based on elution technique
 1. Iso cratic separation
 2. Gradient separation
 - D. Based on the scale of operation
 1. Analytical HPLC
 2. Preparative HPLC
 - E. Based on the type of analysis
 1. Qualitative analysis
 2. Quantitative analysis

Types of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

Normal phase:

Column packing is polar (e.g silica) and the mobile phase is non-polar. It is used for water-sensitive compounds, geometric isomers, cis-trans isomers, and chiral compounds.

Reverse phase:

The column packing is non-polar(e.gC18),the mobile phase is water+miscible solvent (e.g methanol). It can be used for polar, non-polar, ionizable, and ionic samples.

Ion exchange:

Column packing contains ionic groups and the mobile phase is buffer. It is used to separate anions and cations.

Size exclusion:

Molecules diffuse into pores of a porous medium and are separated according to their relative size to the pore size. Large molecules elute first and smaller molecules elute later.

Applications of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

The HPLC has developed into a universally applicable method so that it finds use in almost all areas of chemistry, biochemistry, and pharmacy.

- Analysis of drugs
- Analysis of synthetic polymers
- Analysis of pollutants in environmental analytics
- Determination of drugs in biological matrices
- Isolation of valuable products
- Product purity and quality control of industrial products and fine chemicals
- Separation and purification of biopolymers such as enzymes or nucleic acids
- Water purification
- Pre-concentration of trace components
- Ligand-exchange chromatography
- Ion-exchange chromatography of proteins
- High-pH anion-exchange chromatography of carbohydrates and oligosaccharides

Advantages of High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

- Speed
- Efficiency
- Accuracy

Versatile and extremely precise when it comes to identifying and quantifying chemical compounds.

DRUG PROFILE

Structure of Osimertinib

- **IUPAC Name**—N-(2-{{2-(dimethylamino)ethyl}}(methyl)amino}-4-methoxy-5-

{{4-(1-methyl-1H-indol-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl}amino}phenyl}prop-2-enamide

- **Description** – Osimertinib is a member of the class of amino pyrimidines that is 4-(1-methylindol-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-amine in which one of the amino hydrogens is replaced by a 2-methoxy-4-[2-(dimethyl amino)ethyl] (methyl) amino-5-acrylamidophenyl group. Used (as the mesylate salt) for treatment of EGFR T790M mutation positive non-small cell lung cancer. It has a role as an antineoplastic agent and an epidermal growth factor receptor antagonist. It is a member of indoles, an amino pyrimidine, a biaryl, a secondary amino compound, a tertiary amino compound, a monomethoxy benzene, a member of acrylamides, a substituted aniline and a secondary carboxamide. It is a conjugate base of an osimertinib.

- **Molecular Formula**—C₂₈H₃₃N₇O₂

- **Molecular Weight**—499.619 g·mol⁻¹

- **Solubility** – freely soluble in glacial acetic acid, slightly soluble in methanol, very slightly soluble in water, and practically insoluble in ethanol.

- **Category**—Acrylamides

- Drugs developed by Astra Zeneca
- Ethers
- Indoles
- Lung cancer

- Orphan drugs
- Pyrimidines
- Receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitors.
- **Storage**– store in a cool place, protect from light.
- **Dose** – The manufacturer recommends that breast feeding be discontinued during osimertinib therapy and for 2 weeks after the final dose.
- **Plasma protein binding**–Plasma protein binding of osimertinib is 95%.
- **Bioavailability**– 40-45%
- **Half-life**–The population estimated mean half-life is 48 hours
- **Mechanism of Action**- Osimertinib is an epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) tyrosine kinase inhibitor (TKI) that binds to certain mutant forms of EGFR (T790M, L858R, and exon 19 deletion) that predominate in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) tumours following treatment with first-line EGFR- TKIs. As a third-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitor,

osimertinib is specific for the gate-keeper T790M mutation which increases ATP binding activity to EGFR and results in poor prognosis for late-stage disease. Furthermore, osimertinib has been shown to spare wild-type EGFR during therapy, thereby reducing non-specific binding and limiting toxicity. Compared to wild-type EGFR, osimertinib has 200 times higher affinity for EGFR molecules with the L858R/T790M mutation *in vitro*.

- **Absorption**–
The median time to C_{max} was found to be 6 hours.
- **Route of Elimination** - Osimertinib is primarily eliminated through excretion in the feces (68%), to a lesser extent through urine (14%), while only 2% is excreted unchanged.
- **Volume of Distribution** - The mean volume of distribution at steady state is 918 L.
- **Clearance**-Oral clearance is 14.3 L/hr.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Materials and Method:

Materials:

Active Pharmaceutical Drug

Sr.No.	Name	Description
1.	Osimertinib	White powder, is an anti-cancer medication
2.	Osimertinib 40 Tablet Prescription required strip of 10 tablets	80 mg drug contain each tablet, Manufactured and Marketed by Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd

List of Chemicals use in Research work

Sr No.	Name of Chemical	Molecular Formula	Properties	Manufacturer
1.	Acetonitrile	C ₂ H ₃ N	Solvent, BP76-81.6°C	Merck Life science
2.	Methanol	CH ₃ OH	Flammable Solvent	Merck Life science
3.	Phosphate Buffer	KH ₂ PO ₄	White Crystalline Powder	S D Fine Chem.Ltd, Mumbai
4.	Ortho Phosphoric acid	H ₃ PO ₄	For maintain pH	Merck Life science
5.	Distilled Water	H ₂ O	Universal Solvent, BP 100°C	In house

List of instruments

Sr. No.	Name of Equipment's/ Instruments	Model/ Specification	Manufacturer
1	HPLC	SeriesLC-2030	Shimadzu(Ipromine nce plus)
	Pump	PU2030	
	Sample Injection Port	Auto sampler Injection	
	UV/Vis Detector	UV2030	
	Software	Lab Solution	
2	pH Meter	FP20	Mettler Toledo
3	Balance	Digital XSR	Mettler Toledo
4	Sonicator	UCB-40	Rolex

Methods:**1. Preliminary Analysis of Drug****a) Description**

Color and texture of Osimertinib was compared with reported characters mentioned in drug bank.

b) Solubility

Osimertinib is freely soluble in glacial acetic acid, slightly soluble in methanol, very slightly soluble in water, and practically insoluble in ethanol.

c) UV Analysis

UV analysis was carried out by scanning the solution of Osimertinib at 200-400nm.

1. Selection of detection wavelength

From the standard stock solution further dilutions were done using water and scanned over the range of 200-400 nm and the spectra were overlain. It was observed that drug showed considerable absorbance at 270 nm.

Chromatographic condition:

Compounds were separated using Kromasil C18 (4.6mm x 250mm, 5 μ particle size) column at 40°C

temperature, flow rate 1.00 mL/min with an isocratic mobile phase consisting of Methanol, Acetonitrile and Perchlorate Buffer 3.0 pH of ratio 30:30:40 (v/v/v). Osimertinib were evaluated by UV-VIS detection at 270nm with the injection volume of 10 μ L and the run time 8 min.

Preparation of buffer solution for mobile phase:

250ml perchloric acid was added in 1000 ml water. pH were adjusted to 3.0 with ortho phosphoric acid and solution was filtered through 0.45 micron membrane filter.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Mixed Methanol, Acetonitrile and Perchlorate Buffer 3.0 pH of ratio 30:30:40 (v/v/v). Degas and filter through a 0.20-micron membrane filter.

Preparation of standard solution:

Osimertinib 10 mg, weighed and added in a 50 mL volumetric flask, where they were mixed in 30 mL of mobile phase, sonicated and diluted predetermined volume using mobile phase. Dilute 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with mobile phase and mix. Further dilute 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with mobile phase to get 0.01mg/mL of Osimertinib. A figure 3.3 signifies the typical chromatogram of standards of Osimertinib.

Typical chromatogram of Standards

Preparation of sample solution:

Accurately weighed about 10 mg of tablet powder (Osimertinib) was transferred to 100 ml of volumetric flask containing 60ml of Diluent. The sample was dissolved by sonication for 15 mins and volume was

made up to the mark with Diluent. The resulting solution was filtered using membrane filter 0.22 μ . The filtrate was further diluted appropriately with diluent to get 10 μ g/ml of Osimertinib. This diluted sample was then analysed by HPLC

Typical chromatogram of Samples

Results and Trials:

Trial 1

- Mobile phase-50ml of Water solution and 50 ml Acetonitrile. pH to 4.5 using orthophosphoric acid
- Column:KromasilC18(100mmx2.1mmID, Particlesize:1.7 μ m)
- Flowrate-1.00 ml/min
- Detection wave length(λ max)-270nm
- Injection Volume:10microliter
- Column temperature:Room temperature
- Retention time and Runtime:10.00 Minutes & 6.107Minutes
- Observation and Conclusion- Osimertinib peak eluted this mobile phase, Poor peak shape and minimum theoretical plates. Poor base line and Peak properties not match in this chromatographic condition hence peak is rejected.

Typical Chromatogram of Trial 1

Trial 2

- Mobile phase-50ml of Buffer solution and 50ml Acetonitrile.(50:50 v/v)
- Column:KromasilC18 (100mmx2.1mmID, Particlesize:1.7 μ m)
- Flowrate-1.00 ml/min
- Detection wavelength(λ_{max})-270nm
- Injection Volume:10microliter
- Column temperature:Room temperature
- Runtime:11.00Minutes
- Retention time(RT):Osimertinib–8.704Minutes
- Observation and Conclusion- Osimertinib peaks observed However poor peak properties of this chromatographic condition, Poor peak shape and minimum theoretical plates. Peak properties not match in this chromatographic condition hence peak is rejected.

Typical Chromatogram of Trial 2

Trial 3

- Mobile phase-50ml of Water solution and 50ml Methanol.(50:50v/v)
- Column:KromasilC18(100mmx2.1mmID, Particlesize:1.7 μ m)
- Flowrate-1.00 ml/min
- Detection wavelength(λ_{max})-270nm
- Injection Volume:10microliter
- Column temperature: Room temperature

- Runtime:14.0Minutes
- Retention time(RT): Osimertinib(10.447 Minutes)
- Observation and Conclusion- Osimertinib peak eluted this chromatographic condition, Poor peak

shape and minimum theoretical plates, More retention time as expected and Peak splitting observed. Peak properties not match in this chromatographic condition hence peak is rejected.

Typical Chromatogram of Trial 3

Trial 4

- Mobile phase-60ml of buffer solution and 40 ml acetonitrile.Sonicated with stirring, maintaining the pH to 3.5 using orthophosphoric acid
- Column:PhenomenexC18 (100mmx2.1mmID,Particlesize: 1.7 μ m)
- Flowrate-1.00 ml/min
- Detection wavelength(λ max)-270nm
- match in this chromatographic condition hence peak is rejected.

- InjectionVolume:10microliter
- Column temperature:Room temperature
- Runtime:7.50Minutes
- Retention time(RT):Osimertinib-5.504Min
- Observation and Conclusion- Peak eluted this mobile phase, Poor peak shape and peak properties and minimum theoretical plates. More retention time as expected Peak properties not

Typical Chromatogram of Trial 4

Trial 5 (Optimized Chromatographic Condition)

- Mobile phase-Methanol, Acetonitrile and Perchlorate Buffer 3.0 pH of ratio 30: 30:40 (v/v/v)
- Column:PhenomenexC18(100mmx2.1mmID,Particle size: 1.7 μm)
- Flowrate-1.00 ml/min
- Detection wavelength(λ_{max})-270nm
- InjectionVolume:10microliter
- Column temperature:Room temperature
- Runtime:6.00Minutes
- Retention time(RT):Osimertinib–3.206Min.
- Observation and Conclusion- Peak observed/peak eluted this mobile phase, Poor peak shape and appropriate theoretical plates. Peak properties match with this chromatographic condition hence peak is accepted. Optimized chromatographic condition.

Typical Chromatogram of Trial 5**METHOD VALIDATION****Method validation:****Specificity and system suitability:**

According to ICH Q2R1 requirements for analytical methods, the proposed technique was evaluated for criteria such as specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD, LOQ, and robustness.

Specificity test determines influence of additives on the dissolution outcome. Filtered as well as unfiltered

solutions of blank, placebo, standard as well as samples of Osimertinib were injected and used to evaluate the specificity of the technique.

System suitability study was performed with five replicate analyses of solution of 100

% target concentration of Osimertinib. Several chromatographic parameters were determined, including retention duration, peak area, column efficiency, tailing factor, and resolution between the peaks, and the method was evaluated using these data.

System Suitability Parameter of Osimertinib

System Suitability Parameter		
Retention time(min)	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	3.209
Peak area	15	576998
Theoretical plates		7658
Asymmetric Factor		1.2

Linearity and range:

The development of calibration curves was used to assess linearity. This was accomplished using a standard solution of Osimertinib at various concentrations (50%, 80%, 100%, 120%, and 150%). To construct the calibration curves and correlation

coefficients, all the measurements were carried out also the peak regions of the chromatograms were plotted against the concentrations. Tables represents the results were proportionate to the analyte concentration in the sample and figure 3.5 shows calibration curve of Osimertinib.

Linearity and Range for Osimertinib

Linearity		
Sr.No	Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak Area
1	15	576998
2	30	1153996
3	45	1680994
4	60	2307992
5	75	2884990
6	90	3461988
Slope		38561.77
Standard Error		22625.31

3. Specificity:

Chromatogram of blank was taken as shown in Fig No. Chromatogram of Osimertinib showed peak at are

tention time of 6.632min. We analysed the blank, place bo, Standard and Sample Solution run under same condition, no interference of place bo in standard and sample chromatogram both.

Specificity of Osimertinib by HPLC method

Specificity				
Sample	Label Claim (mg)	Amount Found	Recovery	Retention Time
Tablet	40	39.91	99.775	3.209

Osimertinib marketed formulation

Formulation	
Name of Formulation	Osimertinib40 Tablet
Type of Formulation	Tablet
Concentration(mg)	40

4. Sensitivity:

The sensitivity of measurement of Osimertinib by use of the proposed method was estimated in terms of the

limit of detection(LOD) and the limit of quantification(LOQ).

Osimertinib Sensitivity

LOD&LOQ		
1	LOD(µg/mL)	1.9362
2	LOQ(µg/mL)	5.8673

Precision:**7. System precision & method precision:**

Standard replicates as well as six different sample preparations of similar formulation were used to ensure method precision. The sample solution was

made in the same way as the specified sample preparation procedure. For each analyte, the %RSD was found below 2.0%.

Osimertinib System precision

Precision		
Repeatability		
Sr.No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Peak Area
1	60	2313210
2	60	2293210
3	60	2313223
4	60	2306336
5	60	2363210
6	60	2310998
Average		2316697.8
Standard Deviation		21905.7
RSD%		0.946

Intermediate precision:

Intermediate precision performed by carrying out standard replicate and six independent sample by two different analyst using different chromatographic

system on different days. The chromatographic sample results are summarised in below table

3.3 and 3.4, the %RSD for both analytes obtained was below 2.0%.

Precision Study

Precision			
Sr.No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)		
		Intra day	Inter day
1	60	2313497	2363497
2	60	2306348	2373698
3	60	2311027	2434912
4	60	2292320	2450382
5	60	2363239	2460280
6	60	2310980	2470161
Average		2316235.2	2425488
Standard Deviation		22140.80	41712.85
RSD%		0.9559	1.720

3.5.1.4 Accuracy (Recovery):

It was determined by preparing recovery samples in three copies using standard addition method at 50%, 100% and 150% of standard Osimertinib and

Osimertinib and calculated the % recovery as % label claim and amount recovered. It obtained between 98.0% to 102.0% of labelled amount. The values were given in below table

%Recovery of Osimertinib

Accuracy				
Sr. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Peak area	Found Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	%Recovery
1	48	1834275.2	47.99	99.97
2	60	2292844	59.99	99.98
3	72	917137.6	72.09	100.12

Robustness:

Minor variations in the parameters, like effect of change in flow rate and mobile phase composition, were made intentionally to determine the robustness of the developed RP- HPLC process. But the process remained unaffected by $\pm 0.1\text{mL}$ changes in flow rate and $\pm 5\%$ changes in mobile phase composition. Effect of variation in flow rate the standard and test

solution were produced and transferred into the HPLC system by maintaining flow rate 0.9mL/min , 1.0mL/min and 1.1mL/min . Further it was evaluated for system suitability. The values were given in table Effect of variation in mobile phase the standard and test solution were prepared and transferred into the HPLC system by changing $\pm 5\%$ mobile composition and evaluated system suitability parameter

Robustness of Osimertinib

Robustness					
Sr. No	Parameter		Response	Parameter	Response
MeOH, CAN and Buffer (V/V)			Retention Time(min)	Detection Wave length (nm)	Peak Area
1	59	41		268	
2	60	40	3.209	270	2308180
3	61	39	3.308	272	2341444
Average			3.210	Average	2299830
Standard Deviation			0.080	Standard Deviation	37850.36
RSD%			2.493	RSD%	1.646
Flow Rate (mL/min)			Retention Time(min)	pH of Buffer (mmol/L)	Peak Area
1	0.9			3.34	
2	1		3.209	3	2308353
3	1.1		3.2049	3.2	2232732
Average			3.251	Average	2292446
Standard Deviation			0.0627	Standard Deviation	43733.13
RSD%			1.930	RSD%	1.9077

CONCLUSION

For routine analytical purpose, it is always necessary to establish methods capable of analysing huge number of samples in a short time period with due accuracy and precision. Osimertinib is official in Indian Pharmacopoeia. A very few analytical methods appeared in the literature for the determination of Osimertinib includes HPLC, HPTLC and UV-Visible

spectrophotometric methods. In view of the above fact, some simple analytical methods were planned to develop with sensitivity, accuracy, precision and economical. In the present investigation HPLC method for the quantitative estimation of Osimertinib in bulk drug and per ICH guidelines pharmaceutical formulations has been developed. HPLC methods were validated as and results of linearity, precision,

accuracy, Specificity, System suitability and robustness pass the limit. The HPLC method is more sensitive, accurate and precise compared to the previously reported method. There was no any interference of excipients in their recovery study. The low value of %RSD, molar extinction coefficient ($L \cdot mol^{-1} \cdot cm^{-1}$) suggested that the developed methods are sensitive. The proposed high-performance liquid chromatographic method has also been evaluated over the accuracy, precision and robustness and proved to be convenient and effective for the quality control of Osimertinib. Developed method was found simple and cost effective for the quality control of Osimertinib. Moreover, the lower solvent consumption leads to a cost effective and environmentally friendly Spectroscopic procedure. Thus, the proposed methodology is rapid, selective, requires a simple sample preparation procedure, and represents a good procedure for Osimertinib

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